

Statistical Distributions, Information and a Total Energy Constraint

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Consider a gas with N particles and a physical constraint of total energy E . The energy is distributed over the N particles in some unknown manner. If the average number of particles with energy e_i does not change in time, one may write $n(e_i) = NP(e_i)$ where $P(e_i)$ is probability. The question is: What is $n(e_i)$? We try to derive this quantity in a general manner using information and the total energy constraint. We suggest that $P(e_i) = P(e_i/T)$, i.e. there T is a parameter which makes e_i/T dimensionless and may be used to fix an average energy value which is set equal to the microcanonical total energy E , as an approximation.

In order to determine $P(e_i/T)$ we try to link e_i (energy per particle) to the total energy of the system through the average, i.e. $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i n(e_i)$. In other words, $[n^{-1}] (n) = -e_i/T$ ((1)), which is an obvious statement. Multiplying e_i by $n(e_i)$ and taking δ on $n(e_i)$, yields the change in average energy. On the LHS, however, one has: $\delta \{ n(e_i) [n^{-1}(e_i)] (n(e_i)) \}$. d/dn (from δn) acting on $n(e_i)$ ensures that ((1)) is preserved. If $\sum_i dn(e_i) = 0$, as probability is conserved (i.e. sums to 1), then the second term, namely $n(e_i) d/dn [n^{-1}(e_i)] n(e_i)$ should be a constant. This yields a specific $n(e_i/T)$, namely the Maxwell-Boltzmann one, i.e. $[n^{-1}] = \ln$ (logarithm function). This is equivalent to the information that: $n(e_1)n(e_2)$ is the probability for e_1 and e_2 to interact. This approach is equivalent to the first law of thermodynamics, it seems for the case of no work.

Not all $P(e_i/T)$, however, are solutions of this approach. In particular, a power law probability $P(e_i/T) = A(1 + b(e_i/T)^k)$ is an example, even though it has an inverse function. We present a general approach to finding a function whose d/dn yields $e_i/T * \delta(n)$, but this recipe, used in the literature, requires knowledge of $n(e_i/T)$ while the above approach yields $n(e_i/T)$

Physical Constraints in a Gas

We suggest that a gas of N particles has a physical constraint on the total energy E . Interactions may occur, yielding to a distribution $n(e_i)$ which doesn't change in time. Energy is not created or eliminated, so one may try to equate average energy to the microcanonical E total i.e.

$$E_{total} \approx E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i n(e_i) \quad ((2))$$

E_{ave} and e_i for each particle are considered to be pieces of information in the system. $n(e_i)$, however, must be linked to E_{total} and so one requires one parameter which we call T . $n(e_i) = NP(e_i)$ and $P(e_i)$ is dimensionless, so one wants to remove the units of e_i , i.e. use:

$$e_i/T \quad ((3))$$

At this point, we only have $n(e_i/T)$ which gives no indication of its functional value. The question is: How may one obtain an explicitly form for $n(e_i/T)$? We suggest that a general way to do so is

to link it to the average energy, and, in turn, to changes in this average energy. A basic statement is:

$$[n \text{ inverse}] n = -e_i/T \quad ((1))$$

If one multiplies e_i by $n(e_i)$ and sums over i , one has average energy. Taking delta on $n(e_i)$ yields the change in this average energy. On the LHS, multiplying by $n(e_i)$ and taking delta of the $n(e_i)$ term ensures ((1)) if the second term disappears, namely:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } n(e_i) \Delta \text{ on } n [n \text{ inverse}] n = 0 \quad ((4))$$

It is known that: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } \Delta n(e_i) = 0 \quad ((5))$ due to probability conservation. Thus a solution of ((4)) is :

$$n(e_i) \Delta \text{ on } n [n \text{ inverse}] = \text{constant } \Delta n(e_i) \quad ((6a))$$

Given that $\text{sum over } i \text{ } \Delta n(e_i) = 0$, one may add a constant multiplied by $\Delta n(e_i)$ to ((6a)) i.e.

$$B \Delta n(e_i) + n(e_i) \Delta \text{ on } n [n \text{ inverse}] = \text{constant } \Delta n(e_i) \quad ((6b))$$

In other words, $n(e_i)$ is the solution of a differential equation ((6b)) based on average energy considerations. ((6b)) is a restrictive equation in that it only leads to the ln solution for [inverse n] Not all probability distributions are solutions as a result. For example the power law is one that is not, even though it appears in nature and has an inverse.

The ln = [n inverse] Solution

An immediate solution to ((6b)) for $B=0$ is; $\ln = [n \text{ inverse}]$. ((7))
In such a case: $n \Delta \ln(n) = \Delta(n)$ ((8)). This solution yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution, but seems to be associated with specific physical information related to interactions, namely that:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = \text{the probability for } e_1 \text{ and } e_2 \text{ to interact} \quad ((8))$$

Taking ln of ((8)) allows one to associate $\ln(P(e_1))$ with $-e_i/T$. Thus a mathematical solution of a differential equation ((6)) has built-in physical information associated with interactions. We note that ((8)) may be used to establish reaction balance, i.e. $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)P(e_4)$ so $\ln(P(e_i)) = -e_i/T$.

Power Law Case

It is possible to have a probability: $P(e_i) = A(1 + b(e_i/T)^k)$ [power k]. This is called a power law distribution. There also exists an inverse function:

$$P_{\text{inverse}} = \{(P-A)/Ab\} (\text{power } 1/k)$$

In this case, d/dP of P_{inverse} does not yield $1/P$. Rather: $P d/dP P_{\text{inverse}} = P(e_i) 1/(kAB) \{(P-A)/Ab\} (\text{power } 1/k-1) \delta P$

Thus one does not have a constant times δn and the sum over i is not 0 as it should be. As a result, a power law distribution is not a solution of ((6b)), yet this distribution exists in nature and $P(e)=\text{power law}$ has an inverse. In the next section we consider a general formula for entropy. (As a simple example, one may consider $P(e_i.T) = (e_i/T) (\text{power } n)$ to see that $P d.dP (P_{\text{inverse}})$ is not a constant.

General Formula For Entropy

In ((1)) we consider $[n_{\text{inverse}}] n = -e_i.T$. Here we consider a general form which when extremized applies to any probability distribution $P(e_i/T)$. We use the two constraints:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ e_i P(e_i) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Sum over } i \ P(e_i)$$

Then: $\text{Integral } [P_{\text{inverse}}] + b_1 e_i P(e_i) + b_2 P(e_i) ((9))$ when varied with respect to $P(e_i)$

$$\text{yields: } b_2 + [P_{\text{inverse}}] = -e_i/T \quad \text{if } b_1 = -1/T. ((10))$$

The issue with this approach is that it holds for any $P(e_i/T)$. In other words, it does not yield a solution of $P(e_i/T)$. Rather one must know the form of $P(e_i/T)$ a priori in order to carry out the integral in ((10))

Maximization of Entropy

E_{total} is the physical constraint in the system and it is approximated by $E_{\text{ave}} = \text{Sum over } i \ e_i n(e_i)$. Taking $\delta n(e_i)$ of E_{ave} is part of the process of maximizing a quantity subject to the physical constraint in the problem. In other words:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ n(e_i) [n_{\text{inverse}}] n(e_i) ((11))$$

Is the function to be maximized. It is generally called entropy.

First Law of Thermodynamics

Given that $n(e_i/T)$ depends on the parameter T which fixes E_{ave} (which approximates E_{total}), changing $n(e_i/T)$ by changing T is one way to change the function $n(e_i)$. Such a change is a specific one out of the set of all general changes to $n(e_i)$ such that $\text{Sum over } i \ \delta n(e_i) = 0$.

To see that this condition is explicitly satisfied, consider the normalized:

$$P(e_i/T) = \exp(-e_i/T) / \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T) \quad \text{Let } C = \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T)$$

$$\sum_i dP/dT = -1/T E_{ave} + \sum_i 1/C \exp(-e_i/T) \sum_j e_j/T \exp(-e_j/T)/C$$

$$= -E_{ave}/T + E_{ave}/T = 0$$

This specific change must satisfy the maximization of entropy subject to an average energy condition as a result. This leads to the first law of thermodynamics for no work being done i.e.

$$dE = T dEntropy \quad ((12))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may consider a system with E_{total} approximated by $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i n(e_i)$. We write $n(e_i) = n(e_i/T)$ to obtain a dimensionless argument, with T being a parameter which may be used to fix E_{ave} . At this point, there is no further information on the form of $n(e_i)$. We suggest that $n(e_i)$ may be obtained in a general way by considering changes to E_{ave} in terms of e_i , a single particle energy. In such a case:

$$[n \text{ inverse}] n(-e_i/T) = -e_i/T \quad ((11))$$

To link the RHs of ((11)) with E_{ave} , one may multiply by $n(e_i)$. Taking delta on n yields the change in E_{ave} . The LHS multiplied by $n(e_i)$ and then acted on by delta on n yields a term delta n multiplied by the LHS of ((11)) and a second term, i.e. the LHS of ((4)). This term should equal a constant time delta $n(e_i)$ because the sum over i of this term is 0. This leads to a differential equation with solutions for $[n \text{ inverse}]$ which allow one to find $n(e_i)$ because $[n \text{ inverse}] n = -e_i/T$. The solution is $\ln = [n \text{ inverse}]$. This mathematical solution is associated with physical information, namely that $P(e_1)P(e_2) = n(e_i) = NP(e_i)$ is the probability for e_1 and e_2 to interact.

The approach used here is not based a priori on maximization of entropy subject to a constraint or reaction balance. We show, however, that it is equivalent to both and that in the case of no work, delta n has a specific case of $dn/dT = dT$ which must have the same property of the general dn , namely that $T dEntropy = dE$, where $E = E_{ave}$ and $Entropy = \sum_i n(e_i) [n \text{ inverse}] n$.

The approach outlined yields $[Pinverse] = \ln$, i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution. It does not, however, yield the power law inverse which exists in nature. A more general expression for entropy is given. This may be used if one explicitly knows the form of $P(e_i/T)$ through some other approach.